

The fact that the monoacetyl derivative and its reduction product cannot be converted into a nitrosoamine and that the reduction of the chloral chain of the monoacetyl derivative does not remove the acetyl group proves that on acetylation of (I) the NH group is first acetylated.

To prove that the chloral chain occupies the *para* position to the amino group, oxidation of (I), the mono- and diacetyl derivatives by means of alkaline potassium permanganate was tried. The first two substances did not give pure products. A monobasic acid (III)

melting at 232° was, however, obtained from the diacetyl derivative, which on hydrolysis with 40% potassium hydroxide solution under pressure at 150° produced *p*-methylanino-*m*-toluic acid melting at 201°. This acid was synthesised for mixed melting point determination by the method of Houben (*Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 4490).

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-(α -Hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-*methyl-o*-toluidine hydrochloride.—Equimolecular amounts of methyl-*o*-toluidine (25 g.) and chloral hydrate (35 g.) were mixed and dry powdered zinc chloride (5 g.) added after all the chloral hydrate had gone into solution. The mixture was shaken for 72 hours when it formed a deep green sticky mass. It was heated on a water-bath at 60° for 4 hours and treated with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid, when the solid hydrochloride of the condensation product separated after keeping for 24 hours in a refrigerator. This was filtered off under suction, washed with concentrated hydrochloric acid and dried on a porous plate, yield 13 g. (73%). It was crystallised from 10% ethyl alcohol containing traces of hydrochloric acid and basified with strong ammonia (*vide infra*). The base after crystallising from dilute methyl alcohol was again treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid with a view to obtain a purer specimen of the hydrochloride. This was recrystallised from dilute ethyl alcohol, m.p. 207–8° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 46.7. $C_{10}H_{13}ONCl_4$ requires Cl, 46.5 per cent).

The hydrochloride was converted into the base by grinding the substance in a mortar with strong ammonia. A light green sticky mass

was first obtained which solidified after grinding for 10 minutes and keeping in the ammoniacal solution for 2 hours. The solid mass was powdered, washed well with water and crystallised from methyl alcohol and water as rhombic plates, m.p. 104.5° . (Found: Cl, 39.6. $C_{10}H_{12}ONCl_3$ requires Cl, 39.6 per cent).

The *monoacetyl* (*N*-acetyl) derivative was prepared by heating the base (5 g.) with acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) containing a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid on the water-bath for a few minutes. On keeping overnight the solution was poured over crushed ice and the white solid was washed well with hot water and crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 187° , yield 4.1 g. (Found: Cl, 34.2. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2NCl_3$ requires Cl, 34.3 per cent).

The *diacetyl* derivative was obtained by heating the base with acetic anhydride on the water-bath for 4 hours. The oil, obtained after the solution was poured over crushed ice, solidified on grinding with cold dilute sodium carbonate solution, washing with cold water and keeping in a refrigerator for 24 hours. It was crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 111° , yield 5.4 g. (83.7%). (Found: Cl, 30.2. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3NCl_3$ requires Cl, 30.2 per cent).

The *nitrosoamine* derivative was prepared by adding sodium nitrite solution (25 %) to a cooled solution of the base in a small quantity of absolute alcohol containing a little HCl, when a white precipitate was obtained. The mixture was kept in a freezing bath for 2 hours and the product thus formed was washed with cold water and crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 172.3° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 35.8. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_2Cl_3$ requires Cl, 35.8 per cent).

p-(β -Dichloroethylene)-*o*-*N*-methyl acetotoluidide.—The monoacetyl derivative (40 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (70 c.c.) contained in a glass-stoppered bottle, and zinc dust (11 g.) was added gradually while the mixture was shaken, keeping the temperature at about 40° . After 5 hours the mixture was filtered under suction and the filtrate on dilution and subsequent partial neutralisation with sodium carbonate gave a colourless oil, which was extracted with ether, washed several times with water and distilled at $204^{\circ}/11$ mm. It solidified after keeping for 5 days in a vacuum desiccator containing alkali. The solid was washed with petroleum ether and crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 107.8° , yield 1.5 g. (5%). The same compound was obtained by the reduction of the diacetyl derivative. (Found: Cl, 27.3. $C_{12}H_{13}ONCl_2$ requires Cl, 27.5 per cent).

p-N-Methylacetyl-amino-m-toluic acid.—The diacetyl derivative (10 g.) was suspended in dilute potassium hydroxide solution and a solution of potassium permanganate (3 g; 1.5%) was added gradually, the mixture shaken for 24 hours and then heated on a water-bath (3 hours), when the solution was completely decolourised. The liquid, filtered from the precipitated hydrated manganese dioxide, was concentrated and acidified with strong HCl and the precipitate crystallised from boiling water as white needles, m.p. 232°, yield 2.8 g. (50.5%). (Found: N, 6.8; Eq. wt., 206. $C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 6.8 per cent; Eq. wt., 207).

Hydrolysis of p-N-methylacetyl-amino-m-toluic acid.—Many unsuccessful attempts were made to hydrolyse this acid by means of concentrated hydrochloric acid and by potassium hydroxide at temperatures up to 100°. Eventually the acid (3 g.) was dissolved in 40% potassium hydroxide solution (6 c.c.) and heated at 150° for 6 hours in a sealed tube. The product was dissolved in dilute HCl and the acid precipitated with sodium acetate. It was washed with a little cold water and crystallised from boiling water as white needles, m.p. 201°; soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid and dilute sodium hydroxide. The compound was found to be identical with *p-N-methyl-amino-m-toluic acid* (m.p. 201°), synthesised by the method of Houben (*loc. cit.*), the mixed m.p. being 200°.

p-(α -Hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)ethyl-o-toluidine hydrochloride was obtained from ethyl-o-toluidine and chloral as small rhombic plates from dilute ethyl alcohol, m.p. 210-12° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 44.4. $C_{11}H_{15}ONCl_4$ requires Cl, 44.5 per cent).

The free base, obtained from the hydrochloride by treatment with ammonia, crystallised from carbon tetrachloride, m.p. 107°. (Found: Cl, 37.9. $C_{11}H_{14}ONCl_3$ requires Cl, 37.7 per cent).

The *nitrosoamine*, obtained in the usual manner, crystallises as thick square plates from benzene, m.p. 138° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 34.3. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_2Cl_3$ requires Cl, 34.1 per cent).

The *diacetyl* derivative was prepared in the same way as the diacetyl derivative of *p-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl) methyl-o-toluidine*. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 106-7°. (Found: Cl, 29.2. $C_{15}H_{18}O_3NCl_3$ requires Cl, 29.0 per cent).